

Tightening torque to preload relationship for M6 bolts mounted in softwood using steel washers

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The entire idea was to check a behaviour of a single bolt being embedded in a cuboid wooden sample using steel washers under preloading application. These studies were conducted to discuss gaps in the existing literature. Experimental testing programme was performed with fully threaded M6 5.8 class bolts being embedded in spruce wood of moisture content between 10-13% and density between 420-480 kg/m³ using steel washers with three different diameters.

Several experimental tests were performed, among others, on specimens presented in Figure 1. When necessary properties were determined, the tightening torque (T_f) to preload (F_s) relationship could be found, as presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Exemplary specimens used in experimental tests

Figure 2. Tightening torque to preload relationship determined in experimental tests

Based on the research, a proper tightening torque value that should clamp the M6 bolted connection can be estimated. This can make easier to choose a proper torque wrench to assemble the joint in softwood without introducing too much perpendicular-to-grain plasticisation in wooden members.

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